

REPORT:

*A1.1.2: selection of parameters for
particle-laden flows experiments and
simulations*

Work package 1

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<https://mfmet.eu>

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A1.1.2 M6	Using input from A1.1.1, FOG with support of INESC MN, IPQ, UofG, DTI, LEI, CMI, ALU-FR and CETIAT will select types of particles, methods of particle-laden flow generation, flow path geometries, and methods to characterise velocity, shear stress and particle counting of particle-laden flows with experiments and simulation. The selection will be documented by ALU-FR, FOG, IPQ, INESC MN, LEI and CETIAT in a protocol for an experimental campaign (A1.1.3).	FOG, INESC MN, IPQ, UofG, DTI, LEI, CMI, ALU-FR, CETIAT
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2. Scope

This document describes the selection of types of particles, methods of particle-laden flow generation, flow path geometries, and methods to characterise velocity, shear stress and particle counting of particle-laden flows with experiments and simulation. This report also presents the protocol for an experimental campaign foreseen in A1.1.3.

3. Selection of parameters

To select relevant parameters, the following process has been followed:

- a) From MFMET II A4.1.1, collect end-users and stakeholders' needs in term of particle-laden flows experiments of interest
- b) Collect partners testing and measurement capabilities for particle-laden flows quantities parameters (types of particles, flow path geometries, methods of particle-laden flow generation, measurement methods) of interest for microfluidics / organ-on-a-chip applications related to a).
- c) Select common quantities in a) and b) for which at least two partners have the testing and measurement capability
- d) Check the compliance of c) outputs with MFMET II A1.1.1: selected quantities from c) shall be discussed/addressed in MFMET II A1.1.1 report.

The following figure illustrates the selection process, based on the intersection between participants capabilities, A4.1.1 surveys results and A1.1.1 outputs.

Figure 1: illustrated selection process

The following sections present the selected parameters. For more information about the inputs, please refer to MFMET II A1.1.1 and A4.1.1 reports.

3.1. Types of particles

The following table presents the types of particles selected by each participant for the subsequent (A1.1.3) testing activities:

Table 1: participants' capabilities in terms of types of particles

Partner	Type of particle (capability)	Comment
ALU-FR	Polystyrene beads, bubbles	0.5-5 μm , same density as liquid
INESC MN	Polystyrene beads, bubbles/droplets	$\leq 1 \mu\text{m}$
LEI	Coated (fluorescent) polystyrene beads for PIV, polyester beads for particle-laden flows	5-50 μm
UofG	Polystyrene beads	
CETIAT	Beads, bubbles	Bench compatible with PS beads and bubbles
IPQ	Beads, bubbles	
CMI (simulations)	Simulated spheres	

From A1.1.1 report, the following types of particles are of interest:

- rigid synthetic particles, such as polystyrene or silica microspheres (beads).
- biologically derived particles, such as mammalian cells, extracellular vesicles (EVs), or microbial cells.
- stimuli-responsive or functionalised particles, magnetic beads coated with antibodies, dielectrophoretically active particles, or photoresponsive microcapsules.
- biomimetic particles, such as lipid vesicles (liposomes), hydrogel beads, or cell-mimicking capsules.

The following table presents the selected types of particles capabilities for each participant of the subsequent (A1.1.3) testing activities:

Table 2: selected of types of particles

Type of particle (capability)	Material	Diameter
Beads	Polyester	5-50 μm
	Polystyrene	0.5-50 μm
	Coated (fluorescent) polystyrene	0.5-50 μm
Bubbles	Air on water	0.5-50 μm
Droplets	Oil on water, water on oil, oil/water/oil	0.5-50 μm
Simulated spheres	Any density	Any

3.2. Methods of particle-laden flow generation

The following table presents the selected types of particle-laden flow generation capabilities for each participant of the subsequent (A1.1.3) testing activities:

Table 3: participants' capabilities in terms of particle-laden flow generation methods

Partner	Type of particle (capability)	Fluid	Flow rate range
ALU-FR	double emulsion to create particles, on-chip droplet generation, non contact dispensers	Newtonian	70 to 200 nl/min
INESC MN	stirrers, on-chip droplet generation, heating to generate bubbles on-chips	Newtonian or non-Newtonian	12 nl/min to 1.25×10^8 nl/min
LEI	Syringe pump, pressure controller (0 – 8 bar(g))	Newtonian or non-Newtonian	23.9 nl/min to 100 ml/min
UofG	syringe pumps and pressure controller	Aqueous solution	
CETIAT	syringe pumps and pressure controller	Water, oil	1 to 2×10^4 nl/min
IPQ	syringe pumps and pressure controller	Water, oil	167 nl/min to 1.7×10^6 nl/min
CMI (simulations)	Particles inserted at inlet to a geometry	Any Newtonian liquids with given density and viscosity (possibly temperature)	Any flow rate

From A1.1.1 report, the following types of particle-laden flow generation are of interest:

- suspension injection, in which particles are premixed in a carrier fluid and introduced into the device via pressure-driven flow or syringe pumps.
- on-chip generation of particle-laden flows via co-flow, hydrodynamic focusing, or droplet-based encapsulation.
- droplet microfluidics. Here, discrete droplets of particle-containing fluid are generated in immiscible carrier fluids (typically oils).
- electrokinetic and acoustophoretic methods for generating and controlling particle-laden flows.

The following table presents the selected flow generation methods for the subsequent (A1.1.3) testing activities:

Table 4: selected methods of flow generation

Flow generation	Fluid	Flow rate range
Syringe pump	Water, oil	167 nl/min to 1.7×10^6 nl/min
Pressure controller	Water, oil	12 nl/min to 125×10^6 nl/min
Co-flow / flow focusing	Water, oil	12 nl/min to 125×10^6 nl/min

3.3. Flow path geometries

One possible flow path for the experiments of this protocol is the channel 01 of the MFEMET I glass transfer standard chips manufactured by IMTAG, but only for the design 01 – design 07. Figure 2 illustrates the layouts of the MFEMET I glass transfer standard chips. The dimensions (width, depth, and length) of all Channel 01 are tabulated in Table 5, and they have the same dimensions. Notice that design 08, has no single channel, and thus it cannot be used by this protocol.

Table 5: Dimensions of the main channels of the MFEMET I glass transfer standard chips manufactured by IMT. The channels denoted Channel 01 in Figure 2 are such main channels, and those are intended for use in this protocol. Notice that design 08 cannot be used by this protocol.

Dimensions	Width (mm)	Depth (mm)	Length (mm)
Main channels (green)	1.000	0.100	≈ 40

Figure 2: The layouts of the MFEMET I glass transfer standard chips manufactured by IMT. Channel 01 for design 01 – design 07 are similar and can be used in this protocol. Notice that design 08 cannot be used by this protocol.

New glass chips are being designed for MFEMET II and of these, all channels of design 1(II) and channel 04 of design 4(II) are possible flow path geometries for this protocol. Figure 3 illustrates the layout of

the proposed MFMET II glass chip design 01(II), and Table 6 tabulates its dimensions. The glass chip design 01(II) aims to enable observing particle-laden flows in channels that have serpentine bends or a u-shaped turn, i.e. different from a straight channel.

Table 6: Dimensions of the design 1(II) of the MFMET II glass transfer standard chips designed by IMT. All channels of design 1(II) are possible flow path geometries for this protocol.

Dimension	Value
Channel depth(all)	50µm
Channel width(all)	0.5mm
Channel length(straight)	ca. 40mm
Serpentine length	ca. 70mm
U-shape length	ca. 40mm

Figure 3: Design 1(II) of the MFMET II glass transfer standard chips designed by IMT. All channels of design 1(II) are possible flow path geometries for this protocol. Figure 4 illustrates the layout of the proposed MFMET II glass chip design 04(II), and Table 7 tabulates its dimensions. The glass chip design 04(II) channel 04, aims to enable observing particle laden flows in a channel with a sudden expansion, i.e. different from a straight channel. Perhaps there it will be possible to observe laminar eddies in the sudden expansion. Channel 01 and channel 03, the two uppermost channels in Figure 4, are not intended for this protocol, and instead they are associated with studies of dead volume in Task 1.3 of the project MFMET II.

Table 7: Dimension of the design 4(II) of the MFMET II glass transfer standard chips designed by IMT. Channel 04 (the lower most channel in Figure 4) of design 4(II) is a possible flow path geometry for this protocol. Channel 01 and channel 03, the two uppermost channels in Figure 4, are not intended for this protocol.

Dimension	Value
Channel depth	50µm
Channel width	500µm
Big chambers, length x width	30.4mm x 2.2mm
Big chambers, depth	75µm
Small chamber, length x width	12.5mm x 1.6mm
Small chamber, depth	50µm

Figure 4: Design 4(II) of the MFMET II glass transfer standard chips designed by IMT. Channel 04 (the lower most channel) of design 4(II) is a possible flow path geometry for this protocol. Channel 01 and channel 03, the two uppermost channels in Figure 4, are not intended for this protocol.

3.4. Measurement methods

The following particle-laden flows measurement methods were already established in the MFMET II JRP protocol within the activity A1.1.3:

Table 8: particle-laden flows measurement methods and measured quantities

Partner(s)	Method	Quantity
ALU-FR, INESC MN, LEI	microPIV	Velocity fields / shear stress
	Particle Tracking Velocimetry (PTV)	Particles positions
UofG	Time-lapse imaging	Particles velocities
CETIAT, IPQ	Interface Tracking	Flow velocity, Velocity fields, particles velocities
INESC MN, LEI, UofG, CETIAT, IPQ, ALU-FR	Particle counting	Number of particles per length unit per unit of time

4. Experimental campaign protocol

4.1. Shear stress measurement protocol

This protocol considers measurement of shear stress as a subtopic of measurement of flow velocity fields. Thus, the advised steps for making measurements of shear stress in the laboratory are the same as for measurements of flow velocity, and these may be found in section 4.2. It appears that not all software for control and analysis of PIV and μ PIV, has a feature for calculating shear stress from measurements, see for example PIVlab which is a free and open-source particle image velocimetry (PIV) software (PIVlab, 2025). Thus, this protocol assumes a starting point where flow velocity fields are already available from measurements and use these to derive the shear stress.

As discussed in report A1.1.1 of the MFMET II project (Batista et al., 2025), the viscous stress tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}$, i.e. a tensor with nine stress components, may be inferred from the velocity field \mathbf{v} and the dynamic viscosity μ :

Equation 1

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mu(\nabla\mathbf{v} + (\nabla\mathbf{v})^T)$$

The off-diagonal components of $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ are denoted the shear stresses. Here $\nabla\mathbf{v}$ is the velocity gradient tensor and $(\nabla\mathbf{v})^T$ is the transpose of the velocity gradient tensor. Furthermore, Equation 1 has the assumptions that a fluid is isotropic, incompressible, and Newtonian. For further discussion of Equation 1 and stress tensors in fluid dynamics, please refer to report A1.1.1 and the textbooks by Bird et al., Bruus, Kundu et al., and Lautrup (Batista et al., 2025; Bird et al., 2007; Bruus, 2008; Kundu et al., 2016; Lautrup, 2011).

Equation 1 can be simplified, for example in the special case of cartesian coordinates with a flow confined to the xy plane, and not changing with z , i.e. $\mathbf{v}=(v_x(x,y),v_y(x,y),0)$:

Equation 2

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tau_{xx} & \tau_{xy} & \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{yx} & \tau_{yy} & \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{zx} & \tau_{zy} & \tau_{zz} \end{bmatrix} = \mu \begin{bmatrix} 2\frac{\partial v_x}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y} & 0 \\ \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} & 2\frac{\partial v_y}{\partial y} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Furthermore, if one only considers τ_{xy} in Equation 2:

Equation 3

$$\tau_{xy} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial v_y}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v_x}{\partial y} \right)$$

In case the assumptions of a flow confined to the xy plane and not changing with z are fulfilled, the shear stress τ_{xy} may be calculated from the flow velocity field as described in **Error! Reference source not found.** For cases with different flow geometries, it may be necessary to consult Equation 1 and derive shear stresses equations adequate for those cases. In most cases, the calculation of shear stresses will typically use the dynamic viscosity of the fluid and gradients of the measured flow velocity field.

This protocol suggests calculating the derivatives for gradients of flow velocity fields using finite difference approximations (Olver, 2014; Press et al., 2007). Consider a scalar function $u(x)$, which for example could represent any of the velocity components v_x , v_y , v_z in Equation 1 - **Error! Reference source not found.** The derivative $u'(x)$ may be approximated with the forward finite difference (Olver, 2014; Press et al., 2007):

$$u'(x) \approx \frac{u(x+h) - u(x)}{h}$$

Or the backward finite difference (Olver, 2014):

$$u'(x) \approx \frac{u(x) - u(x-h)}{h}$$

Or the centred finite difference (Press et al., 2007):

$$u'(x) \approx \frac{u(x+h) - u(x-h)}{2h}$$

Where h is the step size, which is assumed sufficiently small to enable neglecting higher order terms. In the context of velocity fields from μ PIV measurements, h could be the distance between two points in the grid of the velocity field, and the values at neighbouring points in the grid, such as $u(x-h)$, $u(x)$, $u(x+h)$, could be a component of the velocity field. Notice that the forward and backward finite differences are first-order approximations to the first derivative, while the centred finite difference is

a second-order approximation to the first derivative (Olver, 2014). Between these, the centred finite difference thus offers the better approximation.

Regarding the finite difference approximation, one could use the forward finite difference for the entire grid and omit the grid's edge with highest x . One could also use the forward finite difference at the grid's edge with the lowest x , the backward finite difference on the grid's edge with the highest x , and the centred finite difference in between.

The calculation of shear stresses outlined in this protocol could be made using programming languages such as Python or MATLAB. Should a project participant have μ PIV software that enables calculation of shear stress directly from measurements that could also be a possibility.

This protocol is similar to examples in the literature that use velocity gradient to calculate shear stress, see for example Lafaurie-Janvore et al. (Lafaurie-Janvore et al., 2016). Though not considered by this protocol, there also exist more advanced methods for calculating shear stress from velocity fields, see for example the Fourier transform traction cytometry discussed by Bashirzadeh et al. and Butler et al. (Bashirzadeh et al., 2018; Butler et al., 2002).

4.2. Flow velocity fields measurement protocol

4.2.1. Particle image velocimetry of beads-laden liquid flows

This section provides a step-by-step protocol tailored for measuring velocity and velocity profiles in particle-laden microfluidic flows within straight rectangular microchannels, accounting for fluid properties, particle characteristics, channel geometry, and PIV system setup. The protocol emphasizes best practices in micro-particle image velocimetry, including cleaning, seeding, optical alignment, calibration, data acquisition, and analysis using PIVlab free and open-source software.

4.2.1.1. Setup and calibration

4.2.1.1.1. Microfluidic chip cleaning and preparation

Microfluidic chips must be thoroughly cleaned to remove contaminants that can obstruct flow or interfere with imaging. For glass chips, use ethanol or IPA followed by demineralized water. Ultrasonic cleaning in a plastic bag with appropriate solvent enhances debris removal without damaging the chip. Ensure chips are air-dried completely before use. Store chips in a clean, particle-free environment to prevent recontamination. Refer to detailed cleaning protocols for specific materials¹.

4.2.1.1.2. Particle seeding

Use microspheres (for example fluorescent polystyrene beads) of a given and relevant diameter range (such as 1–5 μm diameter for example) with density matched to the water-based fluid to ensure neutral buoyancy and minimize sedimentation. Particle concentration should be optimized to provide sufficient seeding density for PIV correlation without causing particle overlap or clustering, which degrades correlation accuracy.

Flow conditions must be checked to be compliant with the expected velocity range and equipment capabilities. In particular, the Reynolds number (Re) should be estimated to confirm flow regime within the microchannel. For a rectangular channel with height H and width W , Re is calculated as:

¹ <https://blog.darwin-microfluidics.com/how-to-clean-your-microfluidic-chip/>
<https://blogs.rsc.org/chipsandtips/2016/02/08/efficient-cleaning-of-a-microfluidic-chip/>

$$Re = \frac{\rho U H}{\mu}$$

where ρ is the fluid density (in kg/m³), U is the mean velocity (in m/s), and μ is the dynamic viscosity (in Pa·s). Laminar flow typically occurs at $Re < 2000$ in microchannels.

4.2.1.1.3. PIV system assembly and alignment

- **Microscope/camera setup:** Mount the microfluidic chip on chip holder in front of the camera or an inverted fluorescence microscope with the objective lens (for example 10× or 20× magnification) focused on the chip's microchannel where the velocity is to be measured. Align the camera and if necessary a lens to satisfy the *Scheimpflug* condition².
- **Light Source and Synchronization:** Connect the pulsed laser or LED light source to the microscope's optical path, ensuring proper excitation and emission filters are in place for fluorescent particles. In case of a pulsed laser source, the synchronizer coordinates the laser pulses and camera frame acquisition with required precision, essential for accurate velocity measurement.
- **Calibration:** Place a calibrated (with an ISO17025 or NMI-traceable calibration certificate) micrometer-scale checkerboard calibration target in the focal plane of the microscope. Capture calibration images at multiple depths to account for optical distortions and to convert pixel displacements to physical units (μm or mm). Use PIVlab's calibration tools to define control points and time steps between frames (Fahrettin Gökhan Ergin, 2018) (John Giardino, 2008).

4.2.1.2. Experimental procedure

4.2.1.2.1. Flow initialization

- Introduce the particle-laden fluid into the microchannel using a syringe pump or pressure-driven flow system. Ensure the flow rate is controlled precisely to achieve the desired velocity range (for example, 0.1–1 mm/s).
- Allow the flow to stabilize before image acquisition to avoid transient effects.

4.2.1.2.2. Image acquisition

- Set the camera exposure time and frame rate to capture particle displacement between images within the maximum allowed for optimal correlation. Frame rates range from depends on flow velocity and magnification.
- Record a series of images in TIFF or raw video format, ensuring the laser and camera are synchronized.
- Monitor the experiment in real-time to detect and correct any issues such as particle aggregation, or laser misalignment.

4.2.1.3. Data processing

4.2.1.3.1. Image pre-processing

- Import images into PIVlab. Apply pre-processing filters such as contrast-limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE) to enhance particle visibility and reduce noise.
- Subtract background images if necessary to improve signal-to-noise ratio.

² https://velocimetry.net/stereo_principles.htm

https://www.seika-di.com/en/measurement/principle_of_piv/piv_system_components.html

4.2.1.3.2. PIV analysis

- Select the region of interest (ROI) within the microchannel where velocity profiles are to be extracted.
- Apply masks to exclude areas with poor particle seeding or reflections.
- Use the multi-pass FFT window deformation correlation algorithm (default in PIVlab) for robust velocity vector calculation. This algorithm iteratively refines the interrogation window size to balance resolution and accuracy.
- Set interrogation window size (e.g., 32×32 pixels) with 50% overlap (value depending on the correlation used), optimized for the expected particle displacement

4.2.1.3.3. Data validation and filtering

- Apply velocity limits and statistical filters (median, standard deviation) to remove erroneous vectors caused by noise or particle overlap
- Use image-based validation filters to ensure vectors correspond to actual particle displacements.

4.2.1.3.4. Calibration and unit conversion

- Calibrate the velocity vectors using the calibration images to convert pixel displacements to physical units (e.g., mm/s).
- Define the time step between frames accurately to compute velocity magnitude.

4.2.1.3.5. Velocity profile extraction

- Extract velocity profiles along the channel centerline or cross-sections using PIVlab's data extraction tools
- Compare experimental profiles with theoretical laminar flow profiles (e.g., parabolic velocity distribution for steady laminar flow).
- Analyze near-wall velocities carefully, accounting for potential wall effects or slip.
- Quantify particle migration effects if particles are not neutrally buoyant or interact with walls.

4.2.1.4. Troubleshooting

Table 9: issues, causes and solutions for PIV measurements

Issue	Cause	Solution
Poor correlation	Low particle seeding density	Increase particle concentration or improve seeding uniformity
Out-of-plane particle motion	Improper focus or alignment	Re-align microscope, ensure Scheimpflug condition is met
High noise in images	Insufficient lighting or exposure	Optimize camera settings, increase light/laser power or exposure time
Erroneous vectors	Particle overlap or noise	Apply stricter validation filters, improve image pre-processing
Channel clogging	Contamination or particle aggregation	Clean chip thoroughly, filter fluids, reduce particle concentration

4.2.2. Specificities of particle image velocimetry of bubbles/droplets-laden liquid flows

In case of bubble or droplet-laden flow velocity or velocity profiles measurements, the general protocol presented in 4.2.1 can be applied. However, the following sections provides a step-by-step guide addressing the specificities for measuring velocity and velocity profiles in bubbles or droplets-

laden flows, applied for an example of velocity measurement within a straight microfluidic channel (100 μm width \times 50 μm height \times 10 mm length), and using PIVlab software for image processing.

4.2.2.1. *Microfluidic Chip Preparation and Cleaning*

- Cleaning protocol:
 - Flush the microchannel with IPA or demineralized water to remove debris.
 - Use an ultrasonic bath (5–10 min) for thorough cleaning.
 - Dry the chip with dry compressed air or nitrogen to avoid residue.
 - Ensure the chip is free of contaminants that could nucleate unwanted bubbles.
- Surface Treatment (Optional):
 - Treat the channel surface (e.g., with plasma or silane coating) to control bubble wetting and adhesion.

4.2.2.2. *Bubble or droplet Generation and Seeding*

- Bubble or droplet generation
 - Use a flow-focusing or T-junction microfluidic device to generate monodisperse bubbles or droplets (in a given diameters range, such as 1–50 μm diameter).
 - Control bubble/droplet size by adjusting gas/liquid flow rates and channel geometry.
 - Ensure bubbles/droplets are stable and uniformly distributed in the flow.
- Flow conditions:
 - Target velocity range (example) : 0.1–10 mm/s.
 - Confirm laminar flow (Reynolds number, $Re = \rho UH/\mu < 2000$).

4.2.2.3. *PIV System Assembly and Alignment*

- Microscope and Camera Setup:
 - Mount the chip on a chip holder in front of the camera or on an inverted microscope.
 - Use backlighting (shadowgraphy) or fluorescence (if bubbles are labeled) for optimal contrast.
 - Align the camera and microscope to satisfy the Scheimpflug condition for uniform focus.
- Light Source and Synchronization:
 - Use a white LED diffuse source, a pulsed LED or laser synchronized with the camera fps.
 - Adjust exposure time to capture sharp bubble/droplet images with minimal motion blur.
- Calibration:
 - Capture images of a micrometer-scale grid to convert pixel displacements to physical units ($\mu\text{m}/\text{mm}$).
 - Calibrate time steps between frames for accurate velocity calculation.

4.2.2.4. *Experimental Procedure*

- Flow Initialization
 - Introduce liquid or gaseous phase flow into the flow-focusing or T-junction microfluidic device using syringe pumps or pressure-driven systems.
 - Allow the flow to stabilize before acquisition.
- Image acquisition
 - Record images at the set framerate, ensuring bubbles/droplets displace 5–10 pixels between frames.
 - Monitor for bubble coalescence, deformation, or out-of-plane motion.

4.2.2.5. Data processing

- Image Pre-processing
 - Import images into PIVlab.
 - Apply contrast enhancement (e.g., CLAHE) and background subtraction to improve bubble/droplets visibility.
- PIV Analysis
 - Define the region of interest (ROI) within the channel.
 - Use multi-pass FFT correlation (recommended interrogation window: 32×32 pixels, 50% overlap).
 - Apply masking to exclude regions with poor bubble seeding or reflections.
- Data validation and filtering
 - Remove erroneous vectors using velocity limits and statistical filters (median, standard deviation).
 - Validate vectors using image-based correlation.
- Velocity Profile Extraction
 - Extract velocity profiles along the channel centerline or cross-sections.
 - Compare with theoretical laminar flow profiles (e.g., parabolic for single-phase flow).
 - Account for bubble-wall interactions and slip effects.

4.2.2.6. Troubleshooting

Table 10: issues, causes and solutions for droplets/bubbles PIV measurements

Issue	Cause	Solution
Poor droplet/bubble visibility	Insufficient lighting/contrast	Optimize backlighting or use fluorescent bubbles/droplets.
Erroneous vectors	Bubble/droplet deformation/overlap	Reduce bubble/droplet size/concentration, improve focus.
Channel clogging	Bubble/droplets coalescence	Adjust flow rates, use surfactants to stabilize bubbles/droplets.
Out-of-plane motion	Misaligned optics	Re-align microscope/camera, ensure Scheimpflug condition.

4.2.3. Method based on the analysis of camera images

4.2.3.1. Front track method

The front tracking method for flow measurements (Batista, 2022), (Elsa Batista, 2021) is an optical method that consists of tracking the position of the bead of a liquid (liquid/air or liquid/liquid interface) inside a (typically) capillary tube over time. This can be replaced by following a specific object inside the liquid like a bead. An optical image acquisition system and image processing software is used to achieve the position over time of the bead. Knowing the displacement of the bead over time and the cross-section area of the capillary, it is possible to calculate the flow rate.

The fluid flow rate related to the front tracking method relates the optically acquired velocity of the fluid ($\frac{x_2 - x_1}{\Delta t}$) to the dimensions of the capillary tube (πr^2). If the flow is measured inside a channel, replace (πr^2) by the channel's cross-section.

Equation 4

$$q_v = \frac{x_2 - x_1}{\Delta t} \pi r^2$$

where:

- x_1 Initial position of the bead,
- x_2 Final position of the bead,
- Δt Time interval between the positions,
- r Capillary section radius.

The capillary tube's material expansion property as a function of temperature $[1 - \gamma (t - 20)]$ is included to take deviation of the dimensions into account.

Equation 5

$$q_v = \frac{x_2 - x_1}{\Delta t} \pi r^2 [1 - \gamma (t - 20)]$$

where:

- q_v Volume flow rate,
- γ Capillary material coefficient of cubic thermal expansion,
- t Calibration liquid temperature.

Similarly, the liquid's thermal expansion during the measurement should be evaluated using Equation 5.

The test method includes calibration of the camera (determining the pixel size), image processing, and determination of position of the bead.

The calibration of the camera determines the relationship between dimensions of a known and calibrated object (for example the outer diameter of the capillary) and pixels of an image. Usually, the output of the camera's calibration is the pixel size in microns (μm).

Image processing facilitates the identification of contours which makes the bead available for accurate positioning. Image processing includes image segmentation, digital image correlation, correction for misalignment, etc.

The determination of the position of the bead is identified by software tools able to find coordinates of the bead, either at reference point(s) along its contour or its average position along the flow direction. Beads positions are determined for each successive image. The bead velocity is calculated as the time derivative (global or on a defined sliding time window) of its successive timestamped positions.

All the instruments used should be calibrated by an accredited laboratory or an NMI/DI.

A typical setup may include:

- Capillary tube (or any other tubing or channel of known dimensions with associated uncertainties)
- High resolution camera
- Image processing software

4.2.3.2. Test protocol

4.2.3.2.1. Preparation

Place all equipment in the room where the test is to be carried out at least 24 hours before starting the measurement.

4.2.3.2.2. Flushing the system

Dead volume in the system may cause entrapment of air and could compromise the integrity of the measurements. Therefore, the system must be flushed prior to calibration start up. Circulating the system with degassed liquid will in time absorb entrapped air. At low flow rates CO₂ and isopropanol alcohol (IPA) are recognized methods to flush air from fluid systems. When flushed, run the system continuously with the calibration liquid until no flushing media is left. In the case of front track all the system is flushed except for the capillary.

4.2.3.2.3. Calibration start-up

Position the calibrated camera in front of the capillary's (or channel) section in which the bead will flow. Adjust the lighting, so that the image has the best contrast for the exposure time that will be used for the measurement. Make sure that the capillary is in focus and align it with the image bottom or top border so that it appears horizontal in the image.

Measure the temperature at the liquid source reservoir and set the flow rate.

4.2.3.2.4. During the calibration

When the stabilization time is reached (typically, if the flow rates remain at $\pm 5\%$ of its target value [3]), acquire timestamped images, and ambient condition data continuously. Check the ambient conditions for fluctuations. If dynamic (fluctuating) flows are to be measured, make sure to choose a framerate sufficiently high (typically equal or superior to 1 frame per second - 1 fps).

4.2.3.2.5. End of calibration

When the calibration time is reached stop the image acquisition and ambient conditions recording.

4.2.3.2.6. Image processing and flow rate calculation

Apply image processing to determine the bead positions in each successive image and calculate the flow as the time derivative of the bead' positions.

The number of repetitions should be at least 3 per flow rate.

4.3. Particle counting measurement protocol

Particle counting methods enable in-line quantification of different types of particles - beads, droplets, bubbles, or cells – by transducing the passage of the object through a specific region of interest along the microchannel into a detectable signal.

4.3.1. Bright field imaging-based counting

Bright field imaging-based counting have been reported for detecting the **droplets** in flow. The method relies on capturing images or video of particles flowing through a microchannel and identifying each droplet through image segmentation. The contrast between the dispersed aqueous phase and the continuous oil phase is used to distinguish the droplet boundaries in bright field illumination. Automated image processing tools are used to detect droplets and count the events in

time. Neto et al. utilized the open-source Bonsai visual programming environment to automatically detect droplet radius, speed and frequency of water-in-oil droplets (Neto et al., 2023). Mudugamuwa et al. used a custom image processing tool developed on MATLAB to characterize droplets in time (Mudugamuwa et al., 2022).

4.3.1.1. Setup

- A backlight illumination directed through the microchannel where the droplets are flowing to provide sufficient contrast of droplet boundaries.
- A high-speed camera mounted to an optical magnification setup (e.g. an inverted microscope equipped with a high-speed camera).
- A computer to run image acquisition software and image processing.
- A flow generator (e.g. a syringe pump or a pressure pump) and a droplet generation chip (e.g. a flow focusing chip) to generate and control the dispersed droplets in the continuous phase.

4.3.1.2. Measurement protocol

- Place the microfluidic device in the optical setup between the camera with an optional magnification lenses and illumination source to ensure backlight illumination while capturing the video/image.
- Prime the microfluidic device with continuous phase and introduce the dispersed phase. Tune the flow rate to achieve a steady droplet generation.
- Adjust the magnification to ensure clear resolution of the droplets. Calibrate the image to record the pixel size (e.g. $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)
- Illuminate the channel such that a sharp droplet boundary appears.
- Acquire the video of droplet flow by image acquisition and processing software. Count each droplet event in time. Other quantities such as droplet speed and droplet size could be tracked by tracking the successive positions of the droplets across the video frames and by referring the calibrated pixel size, respectively.

4.3.2. Fluorescence-based counting

Fluorescence-based counting relies on detection of the light emitted by the fluorescent labelled particles upon excitation. The method has been typically utilized for counting **cells and beads**. The method typically works by hydrodynamically focusing a dilute suspension of fluorescent-labelled particles into a narrow region, illuminating them with a light source (laser or LED), and detecting the emission with a photodetector. As each fluorescent particle passes through the excitation zone, it generates an optical pulse that is converted to an electrical signal. The number of pulses recorded gives the particle count.

4.3.2.1. Setup

- A microfluidic device typically consisting of a channel with a constriction region or a main channel with side channels for sheath flows to focus the particles into a single line.
- A light source – typically a laser diode or LED – to provide excitation at a wavelength matching that of the fluorescent label. The light can be focused on the excitation region on the microchannel via lenses, optical fibre, or waveguide. A fluorescent microscope can be utilized as the optical setup.
- Optical filters to block excitation light and transmit fluorescent signal. In its simplest form, a bandpass filter located in front of the detector can be used.
- A range of photodetectors can be used to sense the events during flow. A photomultiplier tube (PMT) for high throughput application (Li et al., 2018), a PIN photodiode as a more

affordable alternative (Kettlitz et al., 2012), or a CMOS camera (Zhu et al., 2011) can be utilized for this purpose.

- In addition to the optical components, a data acquisition hardware is utilized to digitize the detector signal.

4.3.2.2. *Measurement protocol*

- In advance of counting, a blank buffer is flown to detect the baseline signal. Following the baseline detection, known concentration of particles needs to be flown to determine the threshold needed to identify a signal as an event.
- Place the microfluidic device in the optical setup so that the excitation region on the device is exposed properly.
- Inject the particle suspension at a flow rate selected to ensure that the transit times of the particles through the excitation zone is long enough to generate the pulse.
- Continuously record the fluorescence intensity in time. For PMT and photodiode, the data is a time series of voltage pulses, while for a camera the data is a set of video frames in time. Regardless of whether the detector is analog or digital, further data processing is needed to identify the events.
- For analog detectors, data processing software may need to remove the baseline noise, which can be estimated as an average of dark signal (Li et al., 2018). The signal above a threshold is then counted as an event. For the cameras, image processing identifies the bright spots in each frame of the captured video as events. For either case, the particle count is the sum of the number of events.

4.3.3. Impedance-based counting

An alternating voltage is applied across electrodes typically posed at the base of a microchannel in impedance-based counting. Each particle passing over the electrodes perturbs the impedance signal to produce a pulse. Each pulse is identified as an event. Besides, the amplitude and phase data can be utilized to extract information related to particle size and dielectric properties (Gawad et al., 2001). The method can be used to count **beads, cells, and droplets**.

4.3.3.1. *Setup*

- A microfluidic device comprising a single straight channel with electrodes typically at the bottom of the channel. Side channels connecting to the main channel and carrying a sheath flow can be used to focus the particles into a single stream. Alternatively, the channel can be constricted to force the particles flow along a line. In case of counting droplets, a droplet generator such as a flow focusing microfluidic device is needed.
- An AC excitation source – typically a lock-in amplifier – is needed to apply alternating voltage typically in MHz range across the sensing electrodes and to detect the response signal.
- A flow generator to introduce the particle suspension through the microfluidic device.

4.3.3.2. *The measurement protocol*

- Set AC frequency and amplitude according to the expected particle.
- Introduce a blank buffer into the microfluidic device to detect the baseline impedance.
- Following the baseline detection, introduce the particle suspension into the microfluidic device. Passage of each particle over the electrodes causes a sharp deviation from the baseline. The flow rate should be selected properly. Faster flow rates may result in reduction of signal to noise ratio as – depending on the electronics - it may not be possible to resolve the pulse. On the contrary, slower flow rates limit the throughput.

- Record the voltage or current drop across the sensing electrodes. A third grounded reference electrode can be utilized for differential reading.
- By utilizing a thresholding in real time, detect the peaks and count as events.

4.3.4. Magnetic particle counting

Ensure the fluidic path is clean and unobstructed. Flow the solution with particles labelled with magnetic beads through the magnetic cytometer. Use the dedicated software to collect the voltage signal, correspondent to the magnetic field variation on top of the sensor due to the passage of magnetically labelled particles (Soares et al, 2019). Use the software to collect the number of events corresponding to the passage of magnetically labelled particles.

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